

QUIZ**LAST NAME: RINDAHL****FIRST NAME: STEVEN GLENN****PROGRAM CODE: DCCTH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: Six (6)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US English

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 8

Note: This document is in US letter (8.5"x11") page format

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. The essential elements of a paper are:

- The opening, the body, and the conclusion.
- The introduction, the argument, and the summary.
- The introduction, the body, the conclusion.**¹
- The opening, the argument, and the summary.

2. The thesis of a paper is important. Therefore, it should be placed:

- In the title of the paper.
- As the concluding comment of the introduction.
- Near the center of the introduction before you explain the structure of the paper.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 3.

At, or near, the beginning of the paper.²

3. **Select the wrong statement about the use of *ibid* and *idem*.**

Euclid University recommends the use of *ibid* and *idem* as simple footnote and bibliography references.³

Ibid is from a Latin term meaning “in the same place” and is used in footnotes.

Idem is from a Latin term meaning “the same” and is used in bibliographies.

Although *ibid* and *idem* are still used; they are also sources of confusion to the interested reader. Instead, after the first full reference use a shortened reference in subsequent citations.

4. **As a researcher, what will happen if you write as you read?**

You will get distracted from your research.

Time that should be spent reading will be wasted writing incompletely informed thoughts.

The more you write, the sooner and better you will understand your project.⁴

The result will be numerous disconnected short writings that confuse the flow of your research.

5. **Select the wrong reason to use a quote.**

² Cleenerwerck and Gulma, 14.

³ Cleenerwerck and Gulma, 51.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 34.

- The exact wording constitutes evidence that backs up your reasons.
 - The quoted words are from an authority who backs up your view.
 - Use of multiple quotes demonstrates you are well read in the subject.⁵**
 - The quoted words are strikingly original.
6. **When you must cite multiple sources in a single sentence you should:**
- Use multiple reference numbers (such as ⁵, ⁶) to indicate multiple sources.
 - Choose the most important source and provide citation for it.
 - In a single note, list the citations in the same order in which the references appear in the text; separate citations with semicolons.⁶**
 - Break the sentence into multiple sentences in which only one cited reference exists in each.
7. **Select the wrong footnote formatting rule.**
- Use regular paragraph indents for the footnotes.
 - Single-space each footnote.
 - If there is more than one footnote per page, put a blank line between notes.
 - The footnote must be fully contained on the page it begins.⁷**

⁵ Turabian, 49.

⁶ Turabian, 98–97.

⁷ Turabian, 96.

8. **The quality dissertation includes the following chapters except:**
- The Introduction
 - Literature Review
 - Making the Case⁸**
 - Conclusions and Recommendations
9. **Which of the following is not a reason for the literature review?**
- To prevent the researcher from duplicating existing research.
 - To assist the researcher in situating his or her research within an existing framework.
 - To help the researcher become an expert in his or her field of inquiry.
 - For the researcher to establish preconceptions as to the acceptability of certain types of literature.⁹**
10. **What are the conclusions to your research?**
- Conclusions are another way of saying findings.
 - Conclusions are another way of saying interpretations.
 - Conclusions are statements of what you now know that you did not know prior to the research.¹⁰**
 - Conclusions are independent of the data collected during the research.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications, 2008), 31.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 47.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, 156.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabriru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.